

LOCAL AND NONLOCAL CONTINUUM DAMAGE SIMULATION OF IMPACT AND COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT TESTS ON CFRP LAMINATES

J. Reiner¹ and R. Vaziri²

¹ Composites Research Network, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, B.C., Canada, Hannes.Reiner@composites.ubc.ca

² Composites Research Network, The University of British Columbia, Vancouver, B.C., Canada, Reza.Vaziri@ubc.ca

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ABSTRACT

Continuum damage mechanics is a popular constitutive modelling framework that leads to efficient finite element simulation of intra-laminar damage in composite laminates. Progressive fibre and matrix damage are typically incorporated by strain-softening curves. Here, we use a modified form of the nonlocal continuum damage model, CODAM2, within the explicit finite element software, LS-DYNA, to first calibrate the representative stress-strain response of quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 Carbon Fibre Reinforced Plastic (CFRP) laminates in a fast and robust single element study based on over-height compact tension and compact compression tests. The calibrated damage characteristics are subsequently applied to study the structural response of the laminate under transverse impact and compression after impact tests. Thereby, we compare simulation results with and without the nonlocal regularization feature in CODAM2. The results demonstrate that the nonlocal CODAM2 model is able to predict the force-time response in the impact tests accurately with realistic representation of the extent and size of damage patterns. In contrast, the local simulation of the transverse impact tests shows mesh-dependent damage patterns leading to significantly lower compression after impact strength predictions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Finite element (FE) simulation of the onset and progression of damage in CFRP composite laminates remains a challenging task due to the complex nature of multiple interacting failure mechanisms that are involved. Continuum Damage Mechanics (CDM) is the most popular computationally-oriented constitutive modelling framework that accounts for the intra-laminar failure mechanisms in a smeared manner. The constitutive behaviour in CFRP laminates is governed by damage variables that represent the damage onset and evolution parallel and perpendicular to the fibre direction. The resulting stress-strain responses allow for maintaining the continuity of the FE mesh while simulating the loss of stiffness due to damage.

The COMposite DAMAge Model (CODAM) [1], developed at the University of British Columbia, is an efficient sub-laminate based CDM material model. The second generation of this model (CODAM2) has been introduced [2] with a nonlocal regularization scheme to address both the mesh size and orientation dependencies. This version is available in the commercial explicit FE software, LS-DYNA, as the built-in material card MAT219. Recent modifications to CODAM2 include such features as: (i) a nonlinear in-plane shear response as well as (ii) the incorporation of more general shapes of strain-softening curves other than linear.

One of the key features in orthotropic CDM models is the determination of the appropriate strain-softening curves in the principal longitudinal (fibre) and transverse (matrix) directions. This paper presents an efficient strategy to calibrate these strain-softening curves for use within the modified version of CODAM2. The predictive performance of the calibrated damage model is then validated using published experimental results of low velocity transverse impact and compression after impact

tests conducted on quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 CFRP panels [3, 4]. Specifically, we compare simulation results with and without the nonlocal regularization feature in CODAM2.

2 CALIBRATION OF DAMAGE PARAMETERS

The experimental characterization of the strain-softening response in quasi-isotropic laminates using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [5] is a powerful non-destructive methodology to extract important macroscopic damage properties for the simulation of the structural behaviour of composites. In Over-height Compact Tension (OCT) and Compact Compression (CC) tests, a virtual mesh is generated from the data points obtained by full-field displacement measures. By checking equilibrium at each node of the virtual mesh on the surface of the test specimen, a band of equivalent elements is evaluated at varying distances from the initial notch to identify the damage zone and strain-softening curves. Zobeiry et al [5] applied this strategy to $[90/45/0/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates and used the built-in material model MAT81 in LS-DYNA, which allows laminate strain-softening curves of general shape to be input directly as load curves, to validate the extracted stress-strain responses through DIC in both tension and compression.

Here, we use the same experimental strain-softening data obtained from OCT and CC tests to calibrate the shape of the strain-softening responses in the modified CODAM2 version in tension and compression, respectively. By using known elastic and strength data at the ply level [6], the goal is to find ply-based strain-softening responses in longitudinal and transverse directions such that the essence of the inelastic response of the laminate as obtained by DIC measurements can be captured by CODAM2. Therefore, a single element under uniaxial strain conditions is simulated to enable a comparison of the strain-softening response between CODAM2 and the experimentally determined data [5].

Mode of Loading	Moduli (GPa)			Poisson's Ratio (-)
	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	
Tension	165	9.0	5.8	0.34
Compression	150			

Table 1: Elastic unidirectional input properties for the simulation of IM7/8552 CFRP composites [6].

2.1 Numerical Calibration of Local Damage Parameters

The local formulation of CODAM2 is applied to analyse a single element under uniaxial strain conditions in order to find the optimal softening shapes. Since the considered dispersed $[90/45/0-45]_{4s}$ CFRP laminate under the OCT and CC loading configuration leads to fibre-dominated damage progression, only the softening shape in longitudinal (fibre) direction is optimized. The stress-strain response in the transverse (matrix) direction is assumed to be brittle with a sharp linear softening branch. The elastic input properties are listed in Table 1.

We investigate what ply-based CODAM2 input curves (Figure 1) best fit the average experimental laminate responses (grey curves in Figure 2). Figure 1 shows typical unidirectional stress-strain curves using the modified form of CODAM2. It is found that the best correlation at the laminate level between simulation and experiments in tension is obtained by applying a bilinear softening curve in fibre direction combining an initially steep stress drop followed by a more gradual reduction of stress. In compression, it is important to use a stress plateau to account for fibre kinking and band broadening in a continuous manner. We optimize the input parameters for damage initiation (ϵ_1^i) and damage saturation strains (ϵ_1^s) in tension and compression, respectively.

Figure 2 compares the experimentally obtained stress-strain responses of the laminate [5] with those generated from modified CODAM2 simulations using the input strain softening curves in tension and compression that best fit the experiments. It can be seen that CODAM2 is able to reproduce the experimentally measured average stress-strain curves in tension and compression. Note that the predicted peak stress in both cases is higher than the experimental values.

In order to verify the local calibration of the CODAM2 damage parameters, the obtained softening shapes in tension and compression are applied to the simulation of the OCT and CC tests from where the experimental stress-strain curves in Figure 2 are extracted. The element size in the expected fracture process zone is 1mm x 1mm. Modelling details can be found in other publications such as [7]. Figure 3 shows the resulting force-displacement response of the local version of the modified CODAM2 simulation (in blue) in the OCT and CC test. Similar to the observation in the single element calibration, it can be seen that the overall force-displacement response is well predicted with slightly higher peak forces compared to experimental results.

Figure 1: Typical ply-based stress-strain curves used as input of the modified form of CODAM2 in fibre (left) and matrix (right) direction in the simulation of IM7/8552 CFRP laminates.

Figure 2: Comparison between CODAM2 simulations and experiments [5] of the average tensile and compressive stress-strain responses within the fracture process zone of the $[90/45/0-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates in OCT (left) and CC (right) tests.

2.2 Numerical Calibration of Nonlocal Damage Parameters

The nonlocal CODAM2 formulation requires a nonlocal averaging radius r to consider the state of strain in a finite neighborhood of integration points [2]. This radius r can be linked to the magnitude of the damage height h_c [5]. Zobeiry et al. [8] used $r = 2.0$ mm to simulate successfully the damage progression in $[45/90/-45/0]_{4s}$ laminates of the same IM7/8552 CFRP material. Here, we use the same input for the nonlocal averaging radius (i.e. $r = 2.0$ mm) to simulate the OCT and CC tests mentioned in Section 2.1. The optimal softening shape found in the local calibration scheme in Section 2.1 is applied and the nonlocal damage saturation strains are reduced such that the nonlocal CODAM2 simulations yield similar results compared to its local version. This adjustment to the damage saturation strains is needed to assure equivalent energy dissipation in the nonlocal analysis where damage evolves over multiple rows of elements (compared to the localization along one row of

elements in the local analysis). Figure 3 shows the resulting global force-displacement responses of the nonlocal CODAM2 simulation in OCT and CC tests, left and right figures, respectively. In tension, the nonlocal CODAM2 simulation agrees well with its local counterpart whereas the force response in compression shows a more oscillating behavior with slightly lower forces in the progressive (softening) part of the curve.

Figure 3: Force vs Pin Opening Displacement (POD) curves predicted by local and nonlocal CODAM2 simulations of the Over-height-Compact Tension (left) and Compact Compression (right) tests on $[90/45/0-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates.

3 TRANSVERSE IMPACT SIMULATION

The calibrated damage parameters of the nonlocal CODAM2 are applied to simulate barely visible impact damage in $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates [3]. The impact test is a good validation case for the calibrated model presented in the previous section since it involves a combination of damage in tension and compression.

3.1 Finite Element Model

Figure 4 presents the FE impact model consisting of the impactor, the 150 mm x 100 mm composite plate and a supporting window. The target laminate consists of one shell element through the thickness. The element size is 1 mm x 1 mm, consistent with the previous OCT and CC simulations in Figure 3. This results in 15,000 shell elements to model the composite plate. Note that Sun and Hallett [3] presented high-fidelity solid-cohesive models with over 3 million elements to simulate the same impact test. The CODAM2 results here are compared to these more detailed and computationally intensive discrete model predictions and to experimental measurements [3].

Figure 4: Illustration of the finite element model in LS-DYNA to simulate transverse impact tests on $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates.

The initial velocity of 1.771 m/s results in a transverse impact with incident energy of 10 J. Standard surface-to-surface contact definitions in LS-DYNA are applied between the impactor and the composite plate as well as between the composite plate and the fully fixed rigid supporting window. We will use the calibrated CODAM2 model from the previous section to simulate the impact tests. Since the impact event will incorporate higher strain rates compared to the quasi-static OCT and CC tests, we increase the calibrated saturation strains to account for increasing fracture toughness. It has been shown that the fracture toughness of unidirectional IM7/8552 subjected to high strain rates increases by 30% and 60% in tension and compression, respectively [9, 10]. Table 2 summarizes the adjusted input damage parameters used to simulate the transverse impact test.

Mode of Loading	Simulation Method	Damage Initiation Strains (-)		Damage Saturation Strains (-)	
		Longitudinal ϵ_1^i	Transverse ϵ_2^i	Longitudinal ϵ_1^s	Transverse ϵ_2^s
Tension	Local	0.015	0.013	0.260*	0.015
	Nonlocal			0.202*	
Compression	Local	0.009	0.020	0.48*	0.021
	Nonlocal			0.33*	

* accounting for high strain rates (30% and 60% increase from quasi-static OCT and CC calibration tests in tension and compression, respectively [9, 10])

Table 2: Adjusted ply-based damage properties in tension and compression for the simulation of transverse impact tests in $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates considering the enhancement of fracture toughness at higher strain-rates.

3.2 Results & Discussion

The calibrated CODAM2 damage parameters are applied to one of the low velocity impact tests reported by Sun and Hallett [3]. Figure 5 shows the force-time response of the test compared with simulation results of the local and nonlocal CODAM2 model. In addition, the force response of the high fidelity discrete damage model by Sun et al. [3] is included.

The nonlocal CODAM2 model correlates well with the experimentally measured force profile. It is able to capture the key features of the curve such as the peak force and the instant and magnitude of the load drop at around 1.5 ms. The result of the fully discrete high fidelity model [3] is also in good agreement with the experimental data in Figure 5. The local CODAM2 model shows an early deviation from the linear portion of the curve at around 1 ms. It is also not able to capture the significant load drop compared to the other two modelling techniques. Note that the CODAM2 model only accounts for intra-laminar damage (matrix and fibre) whereas inter-laminar delamination is considered in the high fidelity model. The results in Figure 5 suggest that delamination is only a minor damage mode in this test of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 laminate subjected to impact energy of 10 J. The difference between experiments and the three simulation results in the descending part of the curve can be explained by the presence of permanent displacements which typically form an indentation around the impacted location. None of the discussed simulation techniques accounts for plastic effects such as permanent strains/displacement. The model assumes linear unloading to the origin and this may partially be the reason for the discrepancy between the predicted and measured unloading regimes in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Force vs Time curves of the 10 J transverse impact test applied to $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates. Local and nonlocal CODAM2 predictions are compared with results from experiments [3] and a high fidelity discrete finite element model [3].

The difference between the local and nonlocal CODAM2 results can be explained by investigating the damage patterns in the different plies of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ laminate. Figure 6 illustrates two examples of the predicted matrix damage in the 45° ply and fiber damage in the 0° ply. The contour plots show the corresponding damage variable in the range from 0 (undamaged) to 1 (damage saturation). The white lines in the top left corner of each damage plot indicate the ply's fibre direction. It can be seen that the local CODAM2 simulation results in a highly mesh-dependent and unrealistic damage pattern. These large mesh-dependent bands of damage lead to the early deviation from the experimentally measured force profile.

Predicted damage using the nonlocal CODAM2 model is more confined to the impacted zone which agrees with experimental observations [3] and previous numerical studies [11].

Figure 6: Comparison of the predicted post-impact damage patterns in $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminates between the local and nonlocal CODAM2 version. First row compares matrix damage in the 45° ply and the second row shows the predicted fibre damage in the 0° ply.

4 COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT SIMULATION

The CODAM2 model predictions of the transversely impacted laminates are further subjected to virtual compressive loading for the evaluation of the Compression After Impact (CAI) strength of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ laminate. The study will reveal the effect of the different damage patterns that are predicted in the local and nonlocal impact simulations. As discussed earlier, the permanent indentation due to the localized impact is not captured in the models. When applying their discrete FE model to CAI tests, Sun and Hallett [4] state that indentation has an influence on the local surface deflection in CAI tests. Therefore, the permanent post-impact indentation was manually inserted in their CAI model based on measured DIC displacement data. Here, we neglect permanent indentation since the focus of this study is on the comparison between the local and nonlocal CODAM2 simulations rather than comparison of these models with experiments.

4.1 Finite Element Model

The LS-DYNA restart option is used to perform the CAI simulations. The impactor and supporting window are removed from the FE model of the impact test setup. Two rigid clamps are introduced as shown in Figure 7. The left hand clamp is fully fixed whereas a prescribed displacement is applied to the other clamp. With respect to the damage properties, the damage saturation strains from the transverse impact simulation were modified to account for the change of strain rates. Since the CAI test is quasi-static, the originally calibrated damage parameters based on the quasi-static OCT and CC test are used here.

Figure 7: Left: Set-up of the compression after impact (CAI) finite element model in LS-DYNA showing the post-impact matrix damage in the 45° ply using nonlocal CODAM2. Right: Matrix damage in the 45° ply before the loss of load-carrying capability of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminate using nonlocal CODAM2.

4.2 Results & Discussion

Figure 8 compares the resulting compressive force response of the local and nonlocal CODAM2 simulation applied to the CAI test of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ laminate. The local version with its unrealistic mesh-dependent bands of damage predicts a significantly lower compressive load of 50 kN compared to 76 kN predicted by the nonlocal CODAM2 simulation. Figure 7 shows the damage pattern in the 45° ply post-impact (before the CAI test) and immediately before ultimate failure when the initially confined damage zone has propagated through the entire width of the CAI sample. The CAI simulations show the effect of the large mesh-dependent damage bands predicted by the local CODAM2 simulation. Although the local CODAM2 result correlates fairly well with the force response in the transverse impact test in Figure 5, the large post-impact damage zones propagate faster through the width of the CAI laminate leading to lower predicted CAI strength compared to the nonlocal version of CODAM2.

Note that the experimentally measured compressive load is 112 kN [4]. It is believed that the consideration of permanent displacements and the insertion of inter-laminar delamination in high fidelity FE models will improve the numerical prediction of the CAI strength. The purpose of the presented study is to show the effect of simulated transverse impact behavior in an efficient, continuum damage mechanics based (both local and nonlocal) FE model.

Figure 8: Force vs Displacement curves resulting from the compression after impact simulations of the $[45/0/90/-45]_{4s}$ IM7/8552 CFRP laminate using the local and nonlocal CODAM2 model.

5 CONCLUSION

We presented the calibration and application of a modified form of the continuum damage model, CODAM2, in the finite element software LS-DYNA. In particular, we compared a nonlocal formulation of CODAM2 with its local version by applying it to transverse impact and compression after impact tests through the activation or deactivation of the nonlocal regularization scheme to address both the mesh size and orientation dependencies. After the efficient and robust single-element calibration of the representative stress-strain response of quasi-isotropic IM7/8552 CFRP laminates in tension and compression, over-height compact tension and compact compression tests served as verification for the local CODAM2 simulation and as further calibration step for the nonlocal CODAM2. The calibrated damage characteristics were then applied to study the structural response of the laminate under transverse impact tests and compression after impact tests. The results show that the nonlocal CODAM2 model is able to predict the force response in the impact tests accurately with realistic representation of damage patterns. In contrast, of the transverse impact test simulation using the local CODAM2 shows mesh-dependent damage patterns leading to significantly lower compression after impact strength prediction.

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